

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Studies of the Complexes between UO_2^{2+} and 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid in Aqueous Medium

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The orange-coloured, water-soluble complex, formed by the interaction of uranyl ion and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, has been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous solutions of different ionic strengths and at different temperatures. It has an absorption maximum at 450 m μ and a flat region thereafter. The optimum pH range is 4.5 to 4.8 and it is stable towards time. The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically and conductometrically, is UO_2R (R =roagent). The molecular extinction coefficient is 4.16×10^3 . The dissociation constant of the complex has been determined for different ionic strengths and temperatures. The values of ΔH and ΔS are found to be -5.104 kcal. and 37.2 ± 0.2 e.u. respectively. The probable structure of the complex is also suggested.

The coloured complex, formed by 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid with Fe^{3+} ion, has been investigated by Gupta and Soni¹. Uranyl ion has been found to form an orange, water-soluble complex with 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid with an absorption maximum at 450 m μ and a flat region thereafter. The pH range of constant maximum absorption is between 4.5 and 4.8. Its intensity remains constant even after 24 hours and is stable to wide temperature variations. As no data are available in literature about the nature and composition of the complex formed, an investigation has been made to study these spectrophotometrically, using Job's method of continued variations², slope-ratio method³, and mole-ratio method⁴ and its confirmation by conductometric measurements. The instability constant of the complex has been determined at various temperatures and ionic strengths of the solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard solution of uranium was made from uranyl acetate (B.D.H., A.R.). 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was a B.D.H. L.R. sample and was recrystallised before use. Sodium perchlorate (E. Merck) was used to adjust the ionic strength. HCl and NaOH used were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality.

Absorbance measurements were made by Hilger Uvispec spectrophotometer (Model H 700-308 of Hilger Watts Ltd., London) using one cm effective light path. The cell compartment was fitted with a jacket through which water could be circulated from a thermostat (Townsend & Mercer Ltd., England). A thermometer, inserted into the cell compartment and allowed to come to temperature equilibrium, showed, a variation of less than 0.1° over a period much longer than those needed to make measurements of optical density.

1. *This Journal*, communicated.
2. *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, *x*, 9, 113.
3. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
4. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

Conductometric measurements were made by using conductivity meter (type LBR Wissenschaftlich Technische Werkstätten, Germany). The titrations were carried out in a titration cell (Type LTI) which had a thermostatic jacket for temperature stability. The pH measurements were made by using pH-meter (Philips PR 9400). All the solutions and subsequent dilutions were made with conductivity water.

Spectral Studies—Uranyl acetate solution ($M \times 10^{-3}$) and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid solution ($M \times 10^{-3}$) were taken in the ratio of 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 and absorbances were recorded at different wave lengths. All these solutions showed the maximum absorption at 450 $m\mu$ and a flat region thereafter, thus indicating formation of only one complex⁵. The absorbance due to 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and uranyl acetate is very small at this wave length. All subsequent measurements were therefore carried out at 450 $m\mu$.

Effect of pH.—Solutions containing the same concentration of uranyl ions and the reagent were prepared at different pH values and their absorbances noted at 450 $m\mu$. The complex was found stable at pH range 4.5 to 4.8; hence a pH of 4.5 was selected for subsequent studies.

Effect of Temperature.—Mixtures were heated on a water bath to 85°, cooled to the room temperature, and absorbance was measured after making the volume. There was no difference in the absorption of the sample and that prepared at the room temperature.

Composition of the Complex

Job's Method.—A series of solutions was prepared from $10^{-3}M$ of uranium and the reagent and the quantity $\bar{D}$ (the difference between the total optical density of the solution and that which would be shown by uranyl acetate alone if no reaction occurred) was plotted against the ratio $[\text{UO}_2^{2+}]/([\text{UO}_2^{2+}] + [\text{HO C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{CO}_2\text{H}])$, keeping the pH in each case 4.5. The maximum at 0.5 indicates the formation of the complex containing the uranyl and the reagent in the ratio of 1:1 (Fig 1, curve 1). Curve 2 in the same figure represents the formation of the complex, using acetate buffer of pH 4.5. A marked decrease in the colour of the complex was noticed when the buffer was added.

FIG. 1. Job's method.

Curve 1: Conc. = $1 \times 10^{-3}M$. 2: Using acetate buffer.

FIG. 2. Slope-ratio method.

Curve 1: Uranyl ions varying. Curve 2: Reagent varying.

Slope-ratio Method.—The concentration of the variable component was varied from 5.0×10^{-3} to 4.0×10^{-4} M in presence of excess concentration of 5×10^{-4} M of the constant component. The pH of the solutions was maintained at 4.5. Fig. 2 shows the absorbance ($\bar{D}$) at 450 m μ plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slopes of two straight lines provide the uranyl: reagent ratio as 1:1.

Molar-ratio Method.—A series of solutions was prepared from 1.25×10^{-3} M of the metal and the reagent at pH 4.5, as described earlier, and varying amounts of the reagent were added such that the molar ratio of uranyl to reagent was varied from 1:0.2 to 1:7. Fig. 3 shows a break at a ratio of one mole of the reagent to one mole of uranium.

Molecular Extinction Coefficient and Instability Constant.—Using optical densities of solutions containing a large excess of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid so that as a first approximation the concentration of the complex might be taken equal to that of uranyl ions added, the extinction coefficient of the complex was found to be 4.16×10^3 . The instability constant of the complex:

$$K_{in} = \frac{\{[UO_2^{++}]_{total} - [Complex]\} \{[Acid]_{total} - [Complex]\}}{[Complex]}$$

has been calculated providing the concentration of the complex, obtained from the value of its extinction coefficient. The instability constants of the complex at pH 4.5 were determined at ionic strengths 0.02, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, and 0.20 (Table I).

FIG. 3. Mole-ratio method.

FIG. 4. Variation of log K with $1/T$.

TABLE I

Effect of ionic strength on instability constant of the complex.

	pH=4.5. $\lambda=450$ m μ . Temp.=30°.					
Ionic strength	..	0.02	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
$K_{in} \times 10^{-3}$	..	3.22	3.59	3.95	4.11	4.19

The instability constants of the complex at a constant ionic strength of 0.02 were determined at different temperatures. The results are recorded in Table II. Further, the logarithms of the instability constants have been plotted against $1/T$ (Fig. 4). From the slope of the straight line, ΔH has been found to be -5.104 kcal. Assuming this to be constant over the range of experimental temperatures, ΔS of the reaction has also been calculated as 37.2 ± 0.2 e.u.

TABLE II

Instability constant of the complex at diff. temperatures.

$\mu=0.02$. $pH=4.5$. $\lambda=450$ m μ .

Temp ($^{\circ}K$)	..	293.16	303.10	313.16	323.16	333.16
$K_{in} \times 10^{-3}$	..	4.68	3.22	2.45	1.04	1.44

FIG. 5. Conductance method and pH study.

Curve 1: Conc. = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Curve 2: Conc. = $0.75 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Curve 3: Variation in pH of the reagent by adding uranyl nitrate solution.

Conductometric Studies.—Composition of the complex has been confirmed by conductometric measurements. Curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 5 show the titration curves of 40 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.75 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent vs. $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of uranyl nitrate. From these curves also the ratio of the reagent to uranium is found to be 1 : 1 which confirms the formula of the complex obtained by spectrophotometric measurements.

